

MATERNAL PERCEPTION OF THE TEEN AND EARLY ADULT MOTHERS ON THE POSTPARTUM BLUES AND DEPRESSION

PSYCHOLOGY AND EDUCATION: A MULTIDISCIPLINARY JOURNAL

Volume: 19

Issue 7

Pages: 771-776

Document ID: 2024PEMJ1797

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.11123402

Manuscript Accepted: 03-28-2024

Maternal Perception of the Teen and Early Adult Mothers on the Postpartum Blues and Depression

Alnoury M. Cauring,* Angel Nicole C. Dela Peña, James V. Leuterio

For affiliations and correspondence, see the last page.

Abstract

When it comes to mental health and postpartum, postpartum blues and depression are common disorders that affect mothers and their infants. This study aimed to compare and investigate the maternal perception of early adult and teen mothers experiencing postpartum blues and depression. A descriptive research design was utilized in this paper. Through purposive sampling, a total of 40 selected teen and adult mothers from Brgy. Sarmiento, Parang, Maguindanao del Norte, were respondents to the study. Modified Postpartum bonding questionnaire (PBQ) from Brekington et al (2001) and Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) from Cox et al (1987) were used as tools to determine the maternal views of teen and early adult mothers on the postpartum blues and depression. Results revealed that the maternal perception of teen mothers on the postpartum bonding with their babies have an overall mean of 2.9 which denoted quite often that they have good postpartum bonding with their babies whereas, the adult mothers have a mean of 3.5 denotes very often which indicated that they have very positive postpartum bonding behavior with their babies yet both groups experienced postpartum blues. Moreover, there was a quite significant difference between the two groups of mothers ($t = 2.0134$, $df = 46$, $p\text{-value} = 1.679 < 0.05$). This means that early adult mothers have higher positive postpartum bonding behavior with their babies compared to teenage mothers. It also showed that the majority (70%) of the teen mothers experience depression whereas 30% of them are on suicidal thoughts. Contrarily, 50% of the early adult mothers did not experience depression and suicidal thoughts. Whereas, 30% of them have depression and 20% of them are on suicidal thoughts. The study concludes that early adult mothers have higher positive postpartum bonding behavior with their infants than teen mothers. Along with this, the majority of the teen mother experienced postpartum depression whereas most early adult mothers were less likely to experience depression and suicidal thinking.

Keywords: *postpartum depression, postpartum blues, teen mothers, early adult mothers, suicidal thoughts, maternal, perceptions*

Introduction

The postpartum period begins after childbirth and is typically considered to end within six weeks. Yet, it is the riskiest period for both mothers and newborn babies. With that, 85% of mothers experience postpartum "baby blues" which commonly includes mood swings, crying spells, anxiety, and difficulty sleeping. Whereas, postpartum depression is a temporary depression that about 15% of women following childbirth. It sets generally forms six weeks after giving birth and may last for months, but 25% of mothers were still experiencing depression three years after the birth of their babies. It can also be life-threatening postpartum depression is a factor in 20% of all maternal deaths (Hopkins, 2023). These postpartum blues and depression mainly cause by hormone changes by the dramatic drop in the hormone estrogen and progesterone in the body, genetics or family history of depression, and other external environmental factors (Mayo Clinic, 2023). Postpartum blues are highly treatable with proper and professional help, which of any age can enjoy the reward of motherhood.

The risks and realities associated with teenage motherhood are well documented, with consequences starting at childbirth and following both mother and child over the life span. Teenage births result in health consequences; children are more likely to be born pre-term, have lower birth weight, and have higher neonatal mortality, while mothers experience greater rates of post-partum depression and are less likely to initiate breastfeeding. Teenage mothers are less likely to complete high school, are more likely to live in poverty, and have children who frequently experience health and developmental problems. Understanding the risk factors for teenage pregnancy is a prerequisite for reducing rates of teenage motherhood (Sully, 2020).

Early adult mothers or old mothers are also suffering from postpartum depression because age alone is a risk but some factors are prevalent in older women that may make them susceptible or even no increase of depression but a higher range of pregnancy complications (Morris Psychological Group, 2017). Hence, this study examined to compare the perceptions of teen and young adult mothers on postpartum blues and depression.

Literature Review

Postpartum blues is a low mood and mild depressive symptoms that are transient and self-limited and are extremely common in the perinatal period. This activity describes the diagnostic criteria for postpartum blues and highlights the interprofessional team's role in its evaluation and management (Marwaha, 2023). The postpartum are frequent after giving birth, up to 75% of people experience the baby blues. Yet, three predisposing factors most often found in women who developed postpartum blues were higher levels of depressive symptoms during pregnancy (Morrow & Farr, 2017). Older maternal age is considered to be 40 years and over. The risk, most older women have a healthy pregnancy, however, there is an increase in risks to both mother and baby (Yalom & Lunde, 2000).

Moreover, by its diagnostic criteria, postpartum blues are transient and self-limited. Therefore, it resolves on its own and requires no treatment other than validation, education, reassurance, and psychosocial support. Yet, individuals who are diagnosed with postpartum blues are at increased risk for developing postpartum depression or postpartum psychosis (Balaram & Marwaha, 2023).

However, postpartum depression is a type of depression that happens after having a baby. Up to 15% of persons are impacted. It can cause emotional highs and lows, frequent crying, exhaustion, guilt, and, anxiety, as well as the possibility of difficulty caring for the newborn. With the birth of a child, people go through hormonal, physical, emotional, economic, and social changes. One in five of limited and are these women, or 15%, will experience postpartum depression. But every 1,000 women experience postpartum psychosis. Up to one in seven new mothers after giving birth have these very frequent yet dangerous medical issues (Morrow et al., 2017). For those with significant risk factors, such as a personal or family history of depression, low income, intimate partner violence, having an unwanted pregnancy, or current stressful life events, causing postpartum or perinatal depression (Balaram et al., 2023).

Postpartum depression (PPD) is a mood disorder that affects 10–20 percent of women and can begin any time during the first year after delivery lasting for months. Women with postpartum depression tend to have higher levels of co-morbid anxiety. These women are also more likely to convert to bipolar disorder in the future than women with major depressive disorder without a peripartum onset (Balaram et al., 2023).

Early adults are an introduction to problems, where age is needed for emotional support. Someone at this age experiences changes in responsibility from a student to an independent adult by determining a new lifestyle, taking on new responsibilities, and making new commitments so at this age can be depressed (Mayo Clinic, 2002). Women of advanced maternal age have significantly higher rates of depression than younger women (Muraca & Joseph, 2014). The rate of postpartum depression then steadily declined with increasing age, dropping to 6.5% for 35- to 39-year-olds, before increasing slightly to 6.9% among women 40 and older (Swensen, 2022).

However, postpartum depression is more prevalent among adolescents which likely to be more affected by PPD in terms of prevalence and frequency as compared to adults. It may be a risk factor for poor growth and development in children born to these mothers (Atuhaire & Cumber, 2018). Adolescent mothers are twice as likely as their adult counterparts to have postpartum depression (PPD). It is widely accepted that PPD is more common among adolescent mothers than adult mothers (Ladores & Corcoran, 2019). The risk for postpartum depression is highest among mothers younger than 25 years old according to a survey of more than 1.1 million moms worldwide. By age group, the percentage of women self-reporting postpartum depression symptoms was highest among 18- to 24-year-olds, at 10% (Swensen, 2022). Consequently, counseling and medication are effective treatments for postpartum depression (Morrow et al., 2017).

Methodology

The descriptive research design was utilized in this study in which a survey was taken among teen and early adult mothers to determine their maternal opinions on postpartum blues and depression. Through the purposive sampling method, The participants of the study were 20 teen mothers aged 15-18 years old, and 20 early adult mothers, 19-40 years old who have 0 up to 1-year-old infant(s) from Brgy. Sarmiento, Parang, Maguindanao. Two survey questionnaires were utilized as instruments for gathering necessary data. First, the modified postpartum bonding questionnaire (PBQ) from Brekington et al (2001), the self-report measure assessing maternal perceptions of bonding with their baby. Second, Edinburgh Postnatal Depression Scale (EPDS) from Cox et al (1987) was an effective screening tool and reliable and can validate the measure of depression after childbirth. The data were gathered through descriptive statistical analysis.

Results and Discussion

Table 1. Mean results of maternal perceptions of teen and early adult mothers on the Postpartum bonding with their babies

Statements	Teen mothers		Early adult mothers	
	Mean	Description	Mean	Description
I feel close to my baby.	4.5	Always	4.5	Always
I never thought the old days when I had no baby would come back.	3.5	Very often	4.5	Always
I never felt distant from my baby.	3	Quite often	4.5	Always
I love to cuddle my baby.	4.6	Always	4.5	Always
I never regret having this baby.	2.7	Quite often	4.5	Always
The baby does seem to be mine.	1.7	Sometimes	4.5	Always
My baby does not wind me up.	2.7	Quite often	2.8	Quite often
I love my baby to bits.	2	Sometimes	2.8	Quite often
I feel happy when my baby smiles or laughs.	1.2	Rarely	1.2	Rarely
My baby does not irritate me.	2.9	Quite often	2.7	Quite often
I enjoy playing with my baby.	4.5	Always	4.6	always
My baby does not cry too much.	2.9	Quite often	2.6	Quite often
I never feel trapped as a mother.	1.7	Sometimes	2.6	Quite often
I do not resent my baby.	1.7	Quite often	3.5	Very often
My baby is the most beautiful baby in the world.	1.7	Quite often	2.5	Quite often

I never wish my baby would somehow go away.	4.6	Quite often	3.9	Very often
I never do harmful things to my baby.	2.8	Always	4.6	Always
My baby does not make me feel anxious.	1.8	Quite often	3.6	Very often
19. I am not afraid of my baby.	4.5	Always	4.6	Always
20. My baby does not annoy me.	2.8	Quite often	3.6	Very often
21. I feel confident when caring for my baby.	1.8	Sometimes	2.7	Quite often
22. I never felt the only solution is for someone else to look after my baby.	2.8	Quite often	1.8	Sometimes
23. I never feel like hurting my baby.	4.6	Always	4.5	Always
My baby is easily comforted.	2.6	Quite often	2.7	Quite often
Overall mean	2.9	Quite often	3.5	Very often

The table above shows the result of maternal perception of teen and early adult mothers on the postpartum bonding with their babies. In the view of teen mothers, statements number 4 (“I love to cuddle my baby”), 16 (“I never wish my baby would somehow go away”), and 23 (“I never feel like my hurting baby”) have got the highest mean of 4.6 which denote Always which indicates that they are always doing those bonding with their babies. Bonding is the intense attachment that develops between parents and their baby. It makes parents want to shower their baby with love and affection and to protect and care for their little one. By cradling the baby, it takes the opportunity to be "skin to skin" with the baby by holding him or her against your skin when feeding or cradling which fosters a sense of security and positive self-esteem (Ben-Joseph, 2023). Whereas, statement 9 (“I feel happy when my baby smiles or laughs”) has the lowest mean of 1.2 denotes Rarely which indicates that teen mothers don’t feel happy when their baby smiles or laughs. Hormone changes that happen after birth may cause baby blues. Mothers feel nervous about taking care of their new baby or be worried about how their life has changed since the baby was born. These thoughts can make them feel sad or depressed which most symptoms of postpartum blues (March of Dimes, 2023). Overall, it has a mean of 2.9 denotes Quite often which indicates that the teen mothers have good postpartum bonding behavior with their babies.

Whereas, the maternal view of early adult mothers the statements 11 (“I enjoy playing with my baby”), 17 (“I never do harmful things to my baby”), and 19 (“I am not afraid of my baby”) have the highest mean of 4.6 which denotes Always which indicates that they are always doing those bonding with their babies. Babies have a strong need to be close to their parents. This helps them feel secure and loved, which can help with their development. When babies feel secure, it releases a hormone called oxytocin, which makes them happy and helps their brains grow and develop. Also, playing simple games with the baby is a great way to get to know each other and to make the baby laugh which will help your growing bond (Tommy’s Pregnancy Hub, 2022). Whereas, statement 9 (“I feel happy when my baby smiles or laughs”) has the lowest of 1.2 denotes Rarely which indicates that early adult mothers are not happy when their babies smile or laugh. Due to postpartum blues, mothers went through the motions which erected a wall to separate themselves emotionally from their children and consequently failed to respond to their infants' cues (Beck, 1996). More so, some moms are living with feelings of sadness or depression which shows depressed moods like sadness (Healthline Media, 2023). In general, it has an overall mean of 3.5 denotes Very often which indicates that early adult mothers have very positive postpartum bonding with their babies. Older parents have higher bonding experience as parents because they tend to approach parenthood with more maturity based on both age and life experience. They worry less during the pregnancy, are more positive about becoming parents and generally have a more positive attitude towards their children. They usually spend years, even decades, planning for their babies, saving money to spend on their babies, and simply dreaming about their future children. This extra planning may give them a greater appreciation of the joys of parenthood once that baby is in their arms (Aarhus University, 2017; Duncan, 2023). This implies that both teen and early adult mothers experience postpartum blues but the early adult mothers have higher positive bonding with their babies.

Table 2. Test of Significant Difference between Maternal Perception of Teenage Mothers and Early Adult Mothers on the Postpartum Bonding with Babies

	Teenage Mothers	Early Adult Mothers
Mean	2.9	3.5125
Variance	1.2	1.0211
Stand. Dev.	1.0954	1.0105
n	24	24
t		-2.0134
df		46
p value		1.679

** significant at 0.05 level

The unpaired t-test was used to determine if there is a significant difference between the maternal perception of teenage and early adult mothers on the postpartum bonding with babies. Teen mothers have a mean up to 2.9 or 58% while early adult mothers have a mean of 3.5 or 70% of the highest possible rate. Based on the result in table 2, there is a quite significant difference between the two groups of mothers ($t = 2.0134$, $df = 46$, $p = \text{value} = 1.679 < 0.05$). This led to the rejection of the null hypothesis. This means that early adult mothers have higher positive postpartum bonding behavior with their babies compared to teen mothers. Studies show that older women thrive better during the first part of motherhood. They are more positive about becoming parents, and generally have a more positive attitude toward their children. Children with older mothers -- regardless of their parents' background, education, and finances -- have a better language and have fewer behavioral, social, and emotional problems (Aarhus University, 2017). Whereas, the teen mothers are

also very positive about their experiences of motherhood yet they have often experience quite major difficulties because of their young childbearing (Seamrk & Lings, 2044). Moreover, they displayed higher prenatal and 6-month rates of depression than lower- and higher-resource adult mothers, with significantly more adolescent mothers “consistently” depressed at the two-time points than lower- and higher-resource adult mothers (Lanzi, Bert & Jacobs, 2009). In such analyses, age can be interpreted as an indicator of psychological maturity which a higher maternal age is associated with increased psychosocial well-being during the pregnancy and the early days after the child is born (Aarhus University, 2017).

Figure 1. Percentage of teen mothers who are depressed and on suicidal thoughts.

Figure 1 shows the percentage of teen mothers ($n = 20$) aged 15-18 years old who experienced depression and suicidal thoughts in the past 7 days. A majority (70%) of teen mothers experienced postpartum depression; this may be due to the fact of anxiety, sleepless nights, overwhelming fatigue, difficulty enjoying activities they once did, feeling worthless, and other factors that lead to depression (Mena, 2016). Postpartum depression is more commonly diagnosed among adolescents and may be a risk factor for poor growth and development in children born to these mothers (Atuhaire et al., 2018). Without any experience in raising a child, they constantly worry and lose thoughts about how they can survive. They become easy targets for depression and they will always be surrounded with challenges and problems (Mind Shift Psychological Services, 2018). In teen parents, there is a confluence of multiple psychosocial risk factors, including poverty, lower education level, inadequate social support, and exposure to physical and emotional abuse. These factors increase teen mothers' vulnerability to postpartum depression (Hodgkinson, Beers, Southammakosane & Lewin, 2014). Whereas, 30% of them are on suicidal thoughts which could be the fact the strongest predictors of future suicide attempts, current suicidal ideation, depression, recent attempt by a friend, low self-esteem, and having been born to a teenage mother (Lewinsohn, 2011). Approximately 19% of all 15- to 19-year-olds report having thoughts of suicide, and ~9% have made a suicide attempt. The few available studies of suicidality in adolescent mothers found rates ranging from 11% to 30% and it was estimated to be 38% among low-income adolescent mothers) has been associated with a heightened risk for suicidal behavior (Hodgkinson et al., 2014; Musyimi, Mutiso, Nyamai, Ebuanyi & Ndeti, 2020). More so, the increased suicidal behavior of adolescent mothers is caused by stressors including financial instability and sickness of the new baby (Chin, Wendt, Bennett & Bhat, 2004). Further, this implies that postpartum depression is prevalent to the teen mothers which may also show suicidal behavior if not treated.

Figure 2. Percentage of early adult mothers who are depressed and on suicidal thoughts

Figure 2 shows the percentage of early adult mothers ($n=20$) aged 19-40 years old who experienced depression and suicidal thoughts during and after their pregnancy. Most (50%) participants did not experience postpartum depression and suicidal thinking whereas 30% of them experienced depression whereas 20% of early adult mothers are on suicidal thoughts. In such analyses, most early adult mothers are less likely to experience depression and suicidal thinking because they worry less, are more positive about becoming

parents, and generally have a more positive attitude toward their children because they have more stable relationships, are more educated, and have obtained better access to material resources (Aarhus University, 2017). Whereas, the rate of postpartum depression is declining for old mothers because the percentage of women self-reporting postpartum depression symptoms was highest among 18- to 24-year-olds, but at 10% it drops to 6.5% for 35- to 39-year-olds, before increasing slightly to 6.9% among women 40 and older (Swensen, 2022). The higher maternal age is associated with increased psychosocial well-being during pregnancy and the early days after the child is born (Aarhus University, 2017). Yet, suicidal thinking is present in them. Older adults comprise just 12% of the population, they make up approximately 18% of suicides. Parenthood among 25- to 44-year-olds is associated with lower suicide risk in women, particularly in parents with two or more children (Dehara, Wells, Sjöqvist, Kosidou, Dalman, Sörberg & Wallin, 2021). Thus, it implies that most early adult mothers are less likely to experience postpartum depression and suicidal thinking.

Furthermore, the study recommends further study of the maternal experience of teen and early adult mothers with associated factors like occupation, number of children, and lifestyle. It also recommends investigating their views on paternal support satisfaction.

Conclusion

The study concludes that there is quite a significant difference between the two groups of mothers which the early adult mothers have higher positive postpartum bonding behavior with their infants than the teen mothers. In addition, majority of the teen mother experiences postpartum depression. Whereas, most early adult mothers are seldom to experience depression and suicidal thoughts.

References

- Aarhus University. 2017. "Older Mothers Are Better Mothers, Study Suggests: Children Of Older Mothers Have Fewer Behavioral, Social And Emotional Difficulties." *Sciencedaily*. Sciencedaily, 21. Retrieved On August 12, 2023 From [Www.Sciencedaily.Com/Releases/2017/03/170321110352.Htm](http://www.sciencedaily.com/releases/2017/03/170321110352.htm).
- Atuhaire C. And S.N. Cumber. 2018. Factors Associated With Postpartum Depression Among Adolescents In Uganda. *Pan Afr Med J*. 25;30:170. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From Doi: 10.11604/Pamj.2018.30.170.15333. Pmid: 30455799; Pmcid: Pmc6235503.
- Balaram, K. And R. Marwaha. 2023. Postpartum Blues. In: *Statpearls [Internet]*. Treasure Island (FL): Statpearls Publishing; Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From [Https://Www.Ncbi.Nlm.Nih.Gov/Books/Nbk554546/](https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/Nbk554546/).
- Beck, C. 1996. Postpartum Depressed Mothers' Experiences Interacting With Their Children. Retrieved On August 12, 2023 From [Https://Journals.Lww.Com/Nursingresearchonline/Abstract/1996/03000/Postpartum_Depressed_Mothers__Experiences.8.Aspx](https://journals.lww.com/nursingresearchonline/abstract/1996/03000/postpartum_depressed_mothers_experiences.8.aspx).
- Ben-Joseph, E.O. 2023. Bonding With Your Baby. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From [Https://Kidshealth.Org/En/Parents/Bonding.Html](https://kidshealth.org/en/parents/bonding.html).
- Chin, K., A. Wendt, I.M. Bennett And A. Bhat 2022. Suicide And Maternal Mortality. *Curr Psychiatry Rep*. 2022 Apr;24(4):239-275. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From Doi: 10.1007/S11920-022-01334-3. Epub 2022 Apr 2. Pmid: 35366195; Pmcid: Pmc8976222.
- Dehara, M., M.B. Wells, H. Sjöqvist, K. Kosidou, C. Dalman, C. Sörberg And A. Wallin. 2021. Parenthood Is Associated With Lower Suicide Risk: A Register-Based Cohort Study Of 1.5 Million Swedes. *Acta Psychiatr Scand*. 143(3):206-215. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From Doi: 10.1111/Acps.13240. Epub 2020 Oct 19. Pmid: 33011972; Pmcid: Pmc7983926.
- Duncan, A. 2023. The Unique Struggles And Benefits Older Parents Face. Retrieved On August 12, 2023 From [Https://Www.Verywellfamily.Com/Being-An-Older-Parent-4155772](https://www.verywellfamily.com/being-an-older-parent-4155772).
- Healthline Media. 2023. Motherhood And Depression: How Depression Looks When You Are A Mom. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From [Https://Psychcentral.Com/Depression/Motherhood-And-Depression](https://psychcentral.com/depression/motherhood-and-depression).
- Hodgkinson S., L. Beers, C. Southammakosane And A. Lewin. 2014. A. Addressing The Mental Health Needs Of Pregnant And Parenting Adolescents. *Pediatrics*. 133(1):114-22. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From Doi: 10.1542/Peds.2013-0927. Epub 2013 Dec 2. Pmid: 24298010; Pmcid: Pmc3876179.
- Hopkins, J. 2023. Baby Blues And Postpartum Depression: Mood Disorders And Pregnancy. Retrieved On July 28, 2023 From [Https://Www.Hopkinsmedicine.Org/Health/Wellness-And-Prevention/Postpartum-Moods-Disorders-What-New-Moms-Need-Toknow](https://www.hopkinsmedicine.org/health/wellness-and-prevention/postpartum-moods-disorders-what-new-moms-need-to-know).
- Ladores S. And J. Corcoran. 2019. Investigating Postpartum Depression In The Adolescent Mother Using 3 Potential Qualitative Approaches. *Clin Med Insights Pediatr*. Oct 31;13:1179556519884042. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From Doi: 10.1177/1179556519884042. Pmid: 31700256; Pmcid: Pmc6823974.
- Lanzi, R., S. Bert, And B. Jacobs. 2009. Depression Among A Sample Of First-Time Adolescent And Adult Mothers. Retrieved On August 13, 2023 From [Https://Doi.Org/10.1111/J.1744-6171.2009.00199.X](https://doi.org/10.1111/J.1744-6171.2009.00199.X)
- Lewinsohn, P. M. *Consult Clin Psychol*. 1994 Apr. Psychosocial Risk Factors For Future Adolescent Suicide Attempts Retrieved On

July 5 2023 From <https://pubmed.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/8201067/>.

March Of Dimes. 2023. Baby Blues After Pregnancy. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From <https://www.marchofdimes.org/find-support/topics/postpartum/baby-blues-after-pregnancy>.

Mayo Clinic. 2022. Postpartum Depression Retrieved On July 28, 2023 From <https://www.mayoclinic.org/diseases-conditions/postpartum-depression/symptoms-causes/syc-20376617>.

Mena, K. M. D. 2016. Effects Of Teenage Pregnancy: Mental Health Retrieved On July 5, 2023 From <https://www.healthline.com/health/pregnancy/teenage-pregnancy-effects>.

Mind Shift Psychological Services. 2018. Teen Pregnancy And Its Effect To Mental Health. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From <https://www.mindshiftwellnesscenter.com/teen-pregnancy-and-its-effects-to-mental-health/>.

Morris Psychological Goup. 2013. Postpartum Depression: Are Older Mothers More At Risk? Retrieved On July 29, 2023 From <https://morrispsych.com/postpartum-depression-are-older-mothers-more-at-risk/>.

Morrow, B. And S.L. Farr. 2017. Trends In Postpartum Depressive Symptoms. Retrieved On January 15, 2023 From <https://www.womenshealth.gov/mental-health/mental-health-conditions/postpartum-depression>.

Muraca G.M. And K.S. Joseph. 2014. The Association Between Maternal Age And Depression. J Obstet Gynaecol Can. 2014 Sep;36(9):803-810. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From Doi: 10.1016/S1701-2163(15)30482-5. Pmid: 25222359.

Musyimi, C.W., V.N. Mutiso, D.N. Nyamai, I. Ebuanyi And D.M. Ndeti. 2020. Suicidal Behavior Risks During Adolescent Pregnancy In A Low-Resource Setting: A Qualitative Study. Plos One. 2020 Jul 22;15(7):E0236269. Doi: 10.1371/Journal.Pone.0236269. Pmid: 32697791; Pmcid: Pmc7375578.

Rudoe, N. 2014. Becoming A Young Mother: Teenage Pregnancy And Parenting Policy. Retrieved On August 12, 2023 From <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/abs/10.1177/0261018314526007>.

Seamark, C.J. And P. Lings. 2004. Positive Experiences Of Teenage Motherhood: A Qualitative Study. Br J Gen Pract. Nov;54(508):813-8. Pmid: 15527606; Pmcid: Pmc1324913. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From <https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC1324913/>.

Sully, D. 2021. Postpartum Depression; Postpartum Experiences Retrieved On July 29, 2023 From <https://deidresully.com/tag/postpartum-depression/>.

Swensen, E. 2022. New Study Ids Moms At Highest Risk For Postpartum Depression. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From <https://newsroom.uvahealth.com/2022/02/22/new-study-identifies-moms-highest-risk-postpartum-dression/>.

Tommy's Pregnancy Hub. 2022. Bonding With Your Baby. Retrieved On August 11, 2023 From <https://www.tommys.org/pregnancy-information/after-birth/bonding-your-baby>.

Yalom, I. And D. Lunde. 2000. Postpartum Blues" Syndrome A Description And Related Variables. Retrieved On August 10, 2023 From <https://jamanetwork.com/journals/jamapsychiatry/articleabstract/489540>.

Affiliations and Corresponding Information

Alnoury M. Cauring, LPT, MSciEd
ARMM Regional Science High School
Department of Education – Philippines

Angel Nicole C. Dela Peña
ARMM Regional Science High School
Department of Education – Philippines

James V. Leuterio
ARMM Regional Science High School
Department of Education – Philippines